

Actors Involved in the Exploitation of Industrials Quarries and Their Involvements Strategies

TZETE, Nathalie¹; TATA, N. J¹; DJIBIE, Lionel¹.
Université de DSCHANG

Abstract:- The present work is about the identification of the actors intervening in the activities of industrial exploitation of career to the west Cameroon and their strategies of implication. To carry through this work us have through maintenance guides, collected the data by the different actors. These data have been analyzed with the help of Excel 2010. Here all actors are valued on the socioeconomic and environmental plan. We got for the state-controlled services a total of implication of 43.84% repartee in 55% on the economic plan, 40% on the social plan and 36.66% on the environmental plan. For exploiting them a total of implication of 53.2% repartee in 67.5% on the economic plan, 53% on the social plan and 42% on the environmental plan. For the residents a total of implication of 28.75% repartee in 26.66% on the economic plan, 40% on the social plan and 15% on the environmental plan.

Keywords:- Industrial Career, Grid of Assessment, Actors, West Cameroon.

I. INTRODUCTION

The exploitation of quarries, whether stone, sand or agile, like all other entropic activities, is an activity that has, on the one hand, a considerable impact on the environment. On the other hand, it is an activity that occupies a significant place in the development of the world economy and social well-being.

In the world at large, and in the tropics in particular, state leaders are establishing guidelines to be followed before, during, and after quarries and mineral exploitation. In Cameroon, as part of the management of the mining sector and the impacts related to its activities, the Cameroonian government has implemented a mining code accompanied by numerous application texts the aim of which is to preserve the environment and the safety of people. , promote and encourage research and exploitation of mineral resources necessary for the economic and social development of the country as well as for the fight against poverty. In western Cameroon, there are several quarries, both industrial and artisanal. Due to their impact on land use planning and socio-economic development in this region, our attention will be focused only on industrials quarries. So the question that arises is to know who are the main actors involved in the activity of industrial quarry exploitation? What are their different strategies and degree of involvement? In order to answer these questions, we conducted our study within industrial careers in the West region of Cameroon.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Geographical location of quarries in West Cameroon

To carry out this work we investigated a total of nine (9) industrial quarries in 5 of the 8 divisions of the West region of Cameroon. Figure 1 shows the location map of the differents quarries surveyed.

Fig 1: Presentation of industrial quarries in West Cameroon

According to this figure 1 we have the industrial quarries distributed mainly in the division of Noun (MAKA, KOUPTAMO, GRAVEXO and CAPITSA) then in the division of Nkoug-khi (TESSE and CMG), in the division of Ndé (CREC), the division of Mifi (CHINA LONGTENG) and the division of Bamboutos (ESER).

B. Data collection and analysis

To carry out this work, two types of data were used, namely primary data which was collected using interview guides with the various actors involved in the exploitation of industrial quarries. And the secondary data that were obtained through the bibliographic research of documents related to the theme. The data collected was analyzed using Excel 2010. Indeed, to clearly show the set of actors, we developed an analysis grid with the different actors, and we evaluated them on the basis of the development sustainable.

III. RESULTS

A. The operators of the quarry workers involved and their action strategies for socio-economic and environmental development

In the industrial quarries of West Cameroon, two main types of actors are involved, namely nationals and internationals. Nationals include administrative or state services, operators, and riparian and international communities are made up of quarry managers and managers who are all operators. From the point of view of the activities to be carried out, we mainly have three major groups of actors

involved in the activity of industrial quarry exploitation, namely state services, operators and neighboring communities.

➤ *The state*

Administrative actors are a set of legal persons who are supposed to aim for collective well-being before that of individuals in careers. The ministerial department that intervenes full time in industrial quarries is the Ministry of Mines, Industry and Technological Development (MINMIDT). This ministerial sector in West Cameroon is organized as follows: coordination of the activities of quarries and mines in the region headed by the Regional Delegate; monitoring the activities of the Regional Mining Activities Control Brigades responsible for the Chief of the Regional Mining Activities Control Brigade; The Department of Mines, Geology and Mining Cadastre, placed under the direction of the Chief of Service, is responsible for prepare titles and administrative acts relating to the geological mining sectors, control the execution of action programs in the mining and geology sector, ensure the updating of the provincial map of natural risks as well as the monitoring of activities relating to the mining cadastre having for offices, the Bureau of Mines and Geology, the Bureau of Mining Cadastre and the Regional Laboratory of Mines and Geology. Senior field officers and others for regional monitoring of research programs oriented towards the valuation of raw materials of mineral, agricultural and forestry origin and the implementation of activities relating to mining cadastres.

➤ *Operator*

Operators here represent the people who directly benefit from the activity of quarries. These operators can be nationals or internationals it is generally the businessmen here are the heads or leaders of the subcontractors; Loaders, welders, vehicle and machine drivers, electricians, miners, mechanics, crushing operators and laborers; the trainees as well as the number of staff (managers) ...

➤ *Riverine*

The residents here represent the populations located around the quarry sites generally the spaces occupied by the quarries are spaces which other times were used by these populations for agricultural practice, hunting or even reason fishing. It is for this reason that these populations deprived of this space must be involved as much as possible in order to benefit equitably from this activity.

B. Strategy and involvement of the different actors from a socio-economic and environmental point of view

In quarries activities, the various actors involved are divided into three categories, namely state services, operators, whether national or international, and local residents. The different strategies and their implications in this activity should target the Sustainable Development Goals. Thus, on the basis of the interviews we had with the various stakeholders, we developed a grid in order to assess the

percentages of involvement of these actors. They were assessed on the basis of the model of the three pillars of sustainable development in order to better appreciate their degrees of involvement.

➤ *State plan*

The state, as the guarantor of the security of its populations, through its institutions is responsible for complying with the regulations in force. In the industrial quarries sector in Cameroon, the main state service responsible for monitoring compliance and compliance with the regulations in force on industrial quarries facilities is the Ministry of Mines, Industry and Technical Development. In addition to its regulatory control role, this ministry, through its delegations, must ensure that the quarries activities contributed to socio-economic and environmental development in the locality where it is located. Thus, in western Cameroon, industrial quarries are placed under the supervision of the regional delegation of the West, and the various departmental delegations of the constituencies in which they are implemented. We therefore conducted our interview with the western regional delegation and the departmental delegations on behalf of the various industrial quarries surveyed. Figure 2 shows the percentages of involvement of state actors at the socio-economic and environmental levels.

Fig 2: percentage of involvement of state services from a sustainable development point of view

From Figure 2, we see that state services are more involved in the economic aspect with a percentage of 55% this can be explained by the fact that concerns the area of finance. Here the state ensures that all taxes related to the exploitation of the quarries are respected and carries out if necessary decent rehearsals on site to ensure that this is respected. After the economic component, comes the social component, with a percentage of 40%. We can see through this percentage that the state services at this level do not fully play their role of guarantor of the populations because around

the exploitation sites we find that the state services generally neglect the surrounding populations. Following the social component comes the environmental component with a percentage of 36.66%. This low percentage is explained by the fact that during the various missions of state services, the environmental aspect is not taken into account very much. Most of the time, site visits are only in offices with administrative staff. Figure 3 clearly shows us the meaning of the involvement of state services in the activity of quarries.

Fig 3: orientation of state services in quarrying activities

Figure 3 presents us with a shape of contour defining in a precise way the direction of orientation of the implication of the state services in the activities of exploitation of the quarries on the socio-economic and environmental plan so we can see an isosceles triangle which is more oriented towards the economic aspect. We can therefore conclude that in order for the industrial exploitation of quarries to contribute significantly to sustainable development, the state must review its involvement strategy, particularly on the socio-environmental aspects and improve the economic aspect.

➤ *Operator*

As mentioned above under quarry mining activities, the operator sends to all those whose mining activity represents a source of direct income for it. Operators can be national or international. Note that even if the role of exploitation in general boils down to the search for income, the latter also has the mission of contributing to the socio-economic and environmental development of the locality where the industrial quarry is implemented. Thus, during our research, we had interviews with officials and employ nine industrial quarries surveyed in the West region of Cameroon. Figure 4 gives us the percentages of operator involvement from a socio-economic and environmental point of view.

Fig 4: percentage of operators' involvement from a sustainable development point of view

From Figure 4, we see that the operators are more economically oriented with a percentage of 67.5%. What explains this high percentage is the fact that as we have already mentioned, the activity of the exploitation of the quarries is a purely for-profit activity therefore the owners settle down to make money by exploiting the resource. Following the economy comes the social component with a percentage of 53%. This high percentage is linked to the fact that, although the activity is purely for profit, the operators

have an obligation established by the legislation in force to contribute to the social well-being of the populations located around the quarry. Thus, figure 5 gives us an example of implementation in the community by an operator.

Fig 5: water point built by an operator in Bandjoun TESSE

From figure 5 we can see a water point in a Bandjoun community. This water point was built by Razel Cameroon because it was installed at the TESSE Bandjoun quarry where they mine stones (granite).

Following the social component, comes the environmental component with a percentage of 42%. This percentage is less than 50% this can explain by the fact that although the taking into account of the environment is an obligation, it is still lagging behind because the operators are more focused on the search for the gain even if this must be done to do so at the expense of the environment. We therefore have in Figure 6 the overall orientation of operators in terms of sustainable development.

Fig 6: orientation of operations in quarrying activities

From figure 6, we have a contour shape precisely defining the direction of orientation of the involvement of the operators in the activities of the quarries on the socio-economic and environmental level so we can see a triangle with three different sides which is more oriented towards the economic aspect. We can therefore conclude that in order for the industrial exploitation of quarries to contribute significantly to sustainable development, operators must review their involvement strategies, particularly on the environmental aspect and improve the socio-economic aspects.

➤ *Residents*

The residents represent all the populations located around the quarry, generally these are the populations of the community in which the quarries activity is located. This activity must promote the development of the community where it is located and the community must also be involved in order to take ownership of this development. Around the sites where the nines industrials quarries surveyed are implemented, we had interviews with the populations in order to determine the degree of involvement of the populations in socio-economic and environmental development. Figure 7

gives us the percentages of local residents' involvement in the industrial exploitation of quarries.

Fig 7: percentage of local residents' involvement from a sustainable development point of view

From Figure 7 we see that for residents, they are more involved in the social aspect, with a percentage of 40%. Although this percentage is low, this may explain that in the turn of most of the careers surveyed, the populations seem more interested in their social well-being than anything else and they demonstrate it through multiple claims such as the improvement of roads and other. Following the economic

section we have the social section with a percentage of 26.66%. This explains by the fact that around the quarry sites, although this is not very representative, the populations try as best they can to develop economic activities. Figure 8 gives us the direction of orientation of the residents on the plan sustainable development.

Fig 8: orientation of local residents in quarrying activities

According to figure 8, we have a shape of contour defining in a precise way the direction of orientation of the implication of the residents in the activities of exploitation of the quarries on the socio-economic and environmental plan so we can see a triangle with three different sides which is more oriented towards the social aspect. We can therefore conclude that in order for the industrial exploitation of quarries to contribute significantly to sustainable development, local residents must review their involvement

strategies, in particular on the environmental and economic aspects and improve the social aspects.

➤ *Summary and actor games in industrial quarries*

We have thus assessed each actor involved in the industrial exploitation of quarries in terms of sustainable development in order to determine their degree of involvement in this activity. Figure 9 gives us these different percentages of involvement of the different actors.

Fig 9: percentage of involvement of the different actors from the point of view of sustainable development

From Figure 9, from a sustainable development point of view we see that the operators account for a total of 53.2% followed by state services with a total of 43.84% and in the end residents 28.75%. The percentages of involvement of state services and residents are less than 50%, this is

explained by the fact that both on the side of residents and on the side of state services, mutual efforts must be made to be better involved in the process'activity. Figure 10 shows us the actor game in industrial quarrying.

Fig 10: orientation of the different actors in quarry exploitation activities

According to figure 10, we have a shape of contour defining in a precise way the direction of orientation of the implication of the various actors in the activities of industrial exploitation of the quarries on the socio-economic and environmental plan thus we can see a triangle with three different sides which is more oriented towards operators. We can therefore conclude that in order for the industrial exploitations of quarries to contribute significantly to sustainable development, local residents and state services must review their involvement strategies.

IV. CONCLUSION

At the end of this work, it was about the identification of actors involved in industrial quarries mining activities in West Cameroon and their strategies for involvement. From a sustainable development point of view, it emerges that the various actors involved in the industrial exploitation of quarries still have a lot to do to achieve equitable socio-economic and environmental development. In fact, we have obtained for state services a total involvement of 43.84%, broken down into 55% economically, 40% socially and 36.66% environmentally. For the operators a total involvement of 53.2% divided into 67.5% economically, 53% socially and 42% environmentally. For residents, a total involvement of 28.75% divided into 26.66% economically, 40% social and 15% environmental. It is therefore urgent for all these players to review their strategy of involvement in this industrial quarries exploitations activities.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Bisil, E. 2012. Comment améliorer la rentabilité de la mine pour l'économie du Cameroun : 14 piliers à prendre en compte dans la réforme en cours du code minier
- [2]. Bissou, M., Bamenjo, J.N. et Koagne, A. 2014. Initiative pour la Transparence dans les Industries Extractives (ITIE) et gouvernance minière au Cameroun : entre rhétoriques et réalité. RELUFA Octobre 2014.

- [3]. Evaluation Stratégique Environnementale et Sociale du Secteur Minier au Cameroun: 2016, Renforcement des Capacités du Secteur Minier (PRECASEM) et Evaluation Stratégique Environnementale et Sociale (ESES) (2012 à 2017), Document Principal Tome 1, 355p.
- [4]. Ministère de l'Economie, de la Planification et de l'Aménagement du Territoire (MINEPAT). 2014. Guide de maturation des projets d'investissement public. 68p.
- [5]. Nguējouo, D., Manyacka, E. 2008. Exploitation minière artisanale dans la province de l'Est Cameroun : cas du département de la Boumba et Ngoko, états des lieux : constats, analyses et recommandations. 65p.
- [6]. Nodem, V., Bamenjo, J. N. et Schwartz, B. 2012. Gestion des recettes tirées des ressources naturelles au niveau des collectivités locales au Cameroun : Redevances forestières et minières à Yokadouma, Est du Cameroun. RELUFA 2012 Délégation Régionale MINMIDT Est. Rapports d'activités annuels 2012, 2013 et 2014.